

Graph Neural Networks for Pattern Recognition and Fast Track Finding

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ABSTRACT

Future upgrades to modern high-energy particle detectors will pose considerable challenges for traditional particle track reconstruction methods. Within the past two years, architectures that operate on Graph Neural Networks (GNN) have shown high degrees of promise. Presented here is a unique approach to GNN-based track finding which uses Gaussian mixture techniques to describe track parameter estimates. Unlike traditional methodologies whereby Multi-Layered Perceptrons are employed, the proposed GNN architecture leverages the Kalman filter as a mechanism for information aggregation, in order to iteratively improve the precision of track parameters, as well as for extraction of track candidates compatible with particle motion model. The excitation and inhibition rules of individual edge connections are designed to facilitate the “simple-to-complex” approach for “hits-to-tracks” association, such that the network starts with low hit density regions of an event and gradually progresses towards more complex areas. This paper focuses on the track finding algorithm development and its application on the publicly available dataset designed for the Kaggle TrackML challenge. The preliminary results related to track reconstruction efficiency and purity metrics are presented and discussed. The ultimate aim of this work is to develop a realistic GNN-based algorithm for fast track finding that can be deployed in future high-luminosity phases of particle detector experiments.

PRESENTED AT

Connecting the Dots Workshop (CTD 2022)
May 31 - June 2, 2022

1 Introduction

At its core track finding is a pattern recognition problem, where reconstruction of charged particle trajectories is a highly computationally intensive task. This is particularly problematic for particle detectors during future upgrades, such as the ‘Hi-Lumi LHC’ phase [1] where significant increases in pileup and luminosity will create huge demands for computing power. As many of the existing algorithms do not scale well with a growing data stream, this provides the necessary motivation to explore novel approaches in track finding.

In the past two years, algorithms for track pattern recognition based on GNNs have emerged as a promising technique. Presented here is a unique method that utilises a GNN-based architecture and allows the network to learn patterns as it evolves and iteratively extract track candidates. Individual hits or clusters of hits are modelled as graph nodes and track segments as graph edges. Gaussian mixture techniques are used to approximate track states densities and the Kalman filter (KF) is leveraged as a mechanism for information aggregation, in order to iteratively improve the precision of track parameters, as well as for extraction of track candidates compatible with particle motion model.

Modern silicon detectors typically consist of Pixel and Strip sensors. Here, the application of the GNN-algorithm is focused specifically on the Pixel detector, with the aim that the approach will serve as a sophisticated track seeding technique for pixel clusters and form preliminary track candidates. These seeds can then be extended into the Strips using standard track following. Such an approach could be efficient for saving computational resources if the GNN does not produce large proportions of fake tracks.

This paper is organised as follows; a general description of the GNN-algorithm is presented, and then applications of the algorithm on more specific models are discussed, considering first a toy Monte Carlo (MC) model and then the TrackML dataset [2].

2 GNN Algorithm Development

2.1 Overview

By modelling a GNN node neighbourhood as a Gaussian mixture, the GNN-based track finding is considered as an iterative mixture reduction task which includes masking incompatible node connections (GNN edges) and improving track parameter estimates. By utilising various machine learning techniques, the GNN can identify outlier edges in the network, allowing tracks to be easily extracted. To efficiently exploit a priori knowledge about charged particle dynamics, simplified KFs are embedded in the network and used for two main purposes; firstly as a mechanism for information propagation via message passing and secondly for track extraction.

After the network is initialised, it evolves iteratively through three main stages. The first stage comprises of Gaussian Mixture Reduction (GMR), taking a traditional ML approach to cluster compatible edge states whilst masking outliers. This is followed by an information aggregation stage; by leveraging message passing between nodes in a given neighbourhood, the compatibility of neighbouring states is assessed via extrapolation and application of a KF update. As connections are deactivated, the final stage involves updating the network state. After each stage a track splitting algorithm is applied to identify good track candidates, and if discovered they are extracted via the KF. See Figure 1 for an illustrative flow chart of the main stages of the algorithm, where each iteration comprises of three stages. As the algorithm progresses, the uncertainty in local track orientation decreases and the network will evolve until there are no more candidates that fulfil the criteria for a good track. This is the end state where isolated nodes, track fragments and unresolved ambiguities will remain.

2.2 Network Initialisation

The graph network is constructed using the Python package NetworkX [3], where track hits are represented as nodes and predicted hit-pairs are represented as edge connections. See Section 3.2 for further details on the hit-pair predictor. Following this initial set up, an out-of-the-box Connected Component Analysis (CCA) is applied in order to split the network into smaller, more manageable subgraphs. Within each subgraph,

Figure 1: Flow chart indicating the main stages of the GNN-based algorithm; Gaussian Mixture Reduction (GMR), information aggregation and updating the network state are applied, with track extraction using Kalman filters (KF). After stage 3, a further GMR stage would be applied repeating the iterations.

each node is initialised with a Gaussian vector state representing the local track state estimate, dependent on its neighbourhood.

An illustration of a node and its neighbourhood is shown in Figure 2, where each pairwise connection forms a track state estimate, X_{ij} , initialised with track parameters. See section 3.1 for further details on state implementation. All edges are initialised as active, where each edge has an associated prior probability and edge weight. The prior probability p_{ij} of node i and neighbour node j belonging to the same track is determined, assuming a track can produce at most one hit per layer. The edge weight w_{ij} is a mixture weight for the compatibility of the Gaussian component transmitted from node i to neighbour node j , and represent the strength of the connection. w_{ij} are initialised as uniform weights dependent on the number of neighbours local to a node, and are updated based on how the network evolves. w_{ij} are not to be confused with the traditional weights associated to features within neural networks. As all edges in the graph network are bidirectional, this ensures message passing can occur in both directions with different strength weights, such that the compatibility of the state propagated can be assessed in both directions dependent on its local environment. Given node i and its neighbour nodes j , all track state estimates X_{ij} , associated covariances C_{ij} , priors p_{ij} and mixture weights w_{ij} are stored at node i , forming a weighted Gaussian mixture. For any given node i , the neighbourhood is approximated by a Gaussian mixture given in Eq. (1) where ϕ_{ij} indicates the Gaussian component of pairwise edge connections between nodes i and j .

$$g_i(X) = \sum_j w_{ij} \phi_{ij}(X, X_{ij}, C_{ij}) \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: a) Illustration showing a bidirectional edge connection between nodes A and B, where θ is the angle of inclination to node B from the x axis. b) Initial prior probabilities for node A's edge components given its neighbour nodes B_j , where each B_j are nodes on separate detector layers. The unidirectional connections show that the state information and prior probabilities are being distributed from node A. These entities will differ from nodes B_j distributing to their corresponding neighbourhoods.

2.3 Gaussian Mixture Reduction

For nodes with a high multiplicity of connections (so called “hot” nodes), the number of Gaussian components can quickly rise. To make inferences within a reasonable amount of time, an intermediate approximation step can be used to prevent the number of components of the mixture from exploding. One popular computationally efficient approach for GMR is a clustering-based iterative algorithm. In order to approximate a high order Gaussian mixture by one with lower order, the traditional k-means clustering [4] is used to group together similar edge connections at each node and hence identify outliers which are then deactivated. As the mixture is reduced, Gaussian components that remain active are merged together to form a single merged state and covariance. This merged state is a higher precision track state estimate at each node and is propagated to further stages. GMR forms the first stage of the GNN-based algorithm.

Within k-means, the general case of $k=1$ is used to model the distribution at each node as a single track with some noisy connections. In the case where a vertex sits very close to an intersection point between two tracks, we can expect two or more clusters of edges. However, here the mixture reduction process is declared impossible where all states are propagated to later stages for further processing. This part of the network will wait until competing edges are masked and the mixture becomes more unimodal.

In order to establish whether track states can be grouped into a cluster, a deviation measure is needed to serve as a threshold. The Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence [5] is a measure of the statistical distance between two Gaussian probability distributions and is used to determine the threshold for clustered states. The optimal KL distance used to classify components into a cluster will differ from node to node depending on its neighbourhood. For example, consider a node and its neighbourhood of connections with a high variance of edge orientation. The corresponding KL threshold will be larger in comparison to a node with a small variance of edge orientation, therefore this variance is also used as a discriminating feature. A simulation of 10,000 events, each with seven tracks, is used to build a training dataset and the corresponding MC truth is extracted for pairwise connections. Using the variance of edge orientation in the xy plane for each node and the KL distance between edge components, a Support Vector Machine (SVM) [6] is built to discriminate between the two classes. Other classification algorithms were explored, however the SVM was the most appropriate method to find a decision boundary in order to best separate the classes. Predictions are converted into a look-up-table and is used within the clustering stage.

2.4 Information Aggregation

Neighbourhood information aggregation via message passing is a key feature within graph networks and is leveraged within the second stage of the GNN-based algorithm. At each node, information is propagated to neighbouring nodes for all active edge connections. Once these neighbours obtain information from their own neighbours, state extrapolation and validation is executed.

At each node, the track state is represented by a Gaussian mixture, or a reduced mixture (the merged state $(g_i(X))$). For a given node i , if the merged state was established in the previous stage, this is distributed alongside its covariance matrix to all neighbour nodes j . If a merged state is not available, then all track state estimates are distributed to all neighbours j . The parameter estimation begins with a linear projection onto the subspace of measurements. Each track state estimate is projected via a measurement matrix, which relates the track state to the measurement values. In order to validate if the connection between nodes $i \rightarrow j$ is compatible, the Mahalanobis distance $\Delta\chi_{ij}^2$ is calculated using the residual vector between the projected state HX and the measurement at the neighbour state. If $\Delta\chi_{ij}^2$ is below some threshold d , the connection is compatible and the KF update is applied. If $\Delta\chi_{ij}^2 > d$ then the connection is deemed incompatible and deactivated. The threshold d is a hyper-parameter, representing the maximum $\Delta\chi_{ij}^2$ acceptable.

The KF computes the extrapolated track state estimate \tilde{X}_{ij} using the state transition Jacobian F_i from nodes i to node j and the corresponding extrapolated covariance matrix \tilde{C}_{ij} is given by Eq. (2). The matrix \tilde{C}_{ij} includes the addition of the process noise Q modelled by the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) process [7] which encompasses all material effects. See Section 2.7 for further details. The full derivation of F and Q are shown in Appendix A The KF is implemented using the Python package Filterpy [8].

$$\tilde{X}_{ij} = F_i X_{ij} \quad \tilde{C}_{ij} = F_i \left(\sum C_{ij} + Q \right) F_i^T \quad (2)$$

Figure 3: Track state estimates X_{00} and X_{01} projected from node B_0 to A via the measurement matrix H .

2.5 Updating Network State

As the network evolves and connections are deactivated, the local track orientation for each node changes. Therefore, the corresponding edge component's w_{ij} and p_{ij} are updated. For an edge connection between nodes i and j , the updated edge weights \tilde{w}_{ij} stated in Eq. (4) are computed using the normalised Gaussian measurement likelihood given by Eq. (3). The denominator $\sum_k w_{ik}\beta_{ik}$ is the sum of all weights and likelihoods in a neighbourhood for a given node i . The updated weights \tilde{w}_{ij} are also divided by the number of detector layers on either side of its neighbourhood N_S , in order to account for the probability that a track passing through node i was detected at layer L . For a given node, if any $\tilde{w}_{ij} < 0.1$, these edge connections are automatically deactivated as the likelihood of compatibility of this incoming track state is extremely low. This forms an additional part of the mechanism for edge activation and deactivation. After this update is complete, the iterations repeat and a further GMR would be performed on updated track states.

$$\beta_{ij} = (2\pi|S_{ij}|)^{-1/2} e^{-\Delta\chi_{ij}^2/2} \quad (3)$$

$$\tilde{w}_{ij} = \frac{1}{N_S} \frac{w_{ij}\beta_{ij}p_i}{\sum_k w_{ik}\beta_{ik}} \quad (4)$$

2.6 Track Extraction

Within the GNN-based framework it is possible to iteratively discover good track candidates at each stage of the algorithm as soon as ambiguities are resolved. Therefore, after each stage a track splitting algorithm is applied. Initially an out-of-the-box CCA is used, as the network may have connections which have been deactivated and so a potential subgraph can be separated from the main network. The criteria for good candidates are defined as follows; subgraphs must have a minimum number of four nodes within the volume of interest and must contain one node per layer such that there are no intersecting tracks and no holes. The KF is then applied in order to perform a track fit on all separated networks and iteratively predict and update track parameters. In order to assess the quality of extracted track candidates, the p-value is computed from the χ^2 -based KF track fit quality and must be greater than 0.01.

If a subgraph does not meet the criteria to qualify as a good track candidate, a Community Detection algorithm [9] is applied in order to further partition the set of nodes. Community detection is a generalisation

of CCA and works by using a distance metric, typically modularity, in order to label nodes as ‘closely connected’. Modularity is a benefit function that measures the strength of a particular division of a network using the number of edges. A popular modularity maximisation approach is the Louvain method [10], which iteratively optimises local communities until global modularity can no longer be improved.

Networks with zero extracted candidates are propagated to further stages for additional processing.

2.7 Implementation of Kalman filters

The KF is used for two different functionalities within the GNN-algorithm. The first is to propagate information in the neighbourhood and the second application is for track extraction.

Within the toy MC model each pairwise connection is modelled as a straight line segment. A linear extrapolation is applied during the information propagation stage and the KF is implemented with the addition of a non-zero noise term due to multiple scattering σ_{ms} . This basic approach models an additional source of uncertainty in the track inclination describing the average multiple scattering that a track may experience traversing through a detector and is sufficient to model straight lines trajectories.

However, for the application of the TrackML dataset one must consider the influence of the B-field. This creates a systematic effect on the track and a constant drift in ϕ , as it can bend in a particular direction dependent on the charge of the particle. Statistically such a situation can be described as a correlated noise, which affects track direction and can often be modelled by the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) process [7]. The result is one which can be substituted into the KF as a more sophisticated process noise, making the KF track fit three-dimensional. The process noise Q is implemented with the addition of a non-zero stochastic noise σ_{ou} , as well as the non-zero σ_{ms} . This represents the correlated noise and models the track curvature caused by the presence of the B-field. See Appendix A for further details. Once a potential track candidate is discovered during track splitting, the entire chain of segments is considered and must be compatible with the particle motion model.

An important aspect of the application of the KF here is that reconstruction of curved tracks is possible using a low-dimensionality model. The exact B-field map is not known, however by assuming a slow change in track direction, a special dynamic model for the KF is constructed using the OU process, which implicitly takes into account the track curvature without extending the track state with additional parameters.

3 Applications and results of GNN-algorithm on specific models

3.1 Application for toy MC Model

A 2-dimensional simulation with seven tracks was created, each track with 10 hits, see Figure 4a. The graph network structure was formed using a many-to-one mapping of hits-to-nodes and predicted edge connections were formed between node pairs. For hits in close proximity to one another clusters were formed by determining a suitable threshold and hit merging was executed where necessary, grouping them into 1 node. In order to build edge connections in the graph network and reduce all possible combinatorics an edge-predictor method was devised. The predictor uses a simple calculation whereby the track inclination of neighbouring nodes is calculated. If the inclination of a neighbour node spanning up to two layers apart is contained in a particular range, then this edge is compatible and a connection is established between the nodes. The network is initialised with its corresponding track state estimates X_{ij} , covariance matrices C_{ij} and MC truth particle.

In order to efficiently resolve ambiguities, a method was devised to automatically determine a suitable region for initiating the pattern recognition. For a given node, the variance of edge orientation σ_e^2 of its neighbourhood was considered. Figure 4b shows a heat map, indicating “hot” nodes (white) which represent nodes with a high degree (number of edges associated to the node), whereas “cold” nodes (orange - red) indicate regions with fewer ambiguities to resolve. This indicates that the node degree is an indirect characteristic of how messy a local neighbourhood is and provides a method to determine where pattern recognition should begin on a graph network in order to resolve incompatible edge connections. Nodes

with $\sigma_e^2 > 0.8$ were temporarily removed and the pattern recognition was initially applied to the remaining network.

Each pairwise connection between two nodes forms a track state estimate X_{ij} and is given by Eq. (5). X_{ij} comprises of the measurement at node i , m_i and the track inclination to the neighbouring node j , given by $t_{ij} = (m_i - m_j)/(x_i - x_j)$, modelling the segment as a straight line. The edge covariance matrix, S , for connections $i \rightarrow j$ are stated in Eq. (5), where σ_0^2 is the error due to measurement in the xy plane initialised to $100\mu m$. Additionally, negligible error is assumed in the x measurement due to the high precision of Pixel sensors. Matrix G relates the measurements to the state vector X_{ij} using a linear extrapolation where $dx = x_i - x_j$. The state covariance C_{ij} is derived using the standard linear algebra approach, where $C_{ij} = GSG^T$.

$$X_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} m_i \\ t_{ij} \end{bmatrix} \quad S = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_0^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_0^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad G = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1/dx & -1/dx \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Figure 4: a) Simple 2-dimensional simulation of seven truth tracks where each track contains ten hits; one hit per layer. Each colour represents a different track. b) Conversion of the simulated hits in a) plotted as a Graph Network. The network contains a many-to-one mapping of hits to nodes, merging close proximity nodes where necessary and predicted edge connections are formed using a pair predictor. The heat map represents node degree, where “hot” nodes (white) contain many edge connections, whereas “cold” nodes (orange - red) contain fewer edge connections.

Figure 5 shows an example of the GNN-based algorithm described in Section 2 applied to this simulated network. Figure 5a displays the simulated network where nodes with $\sigma_e^2 > 0.8$ have been removed and a CCA has been applied, reducing the computational complexity in further stages as three smaller subgraphs have been identified. The extracted track candidates are shown in Figure 5b. Outlier edge connections have been successfully removed, as this particular simulation shows successful extraction of all seven truth tracks within two stages.

Figure 6 shows another simulation of a simple track model with application of the GNN algorithm. Similarly, nodes with $\sigma_e^2 > 0.8$ have been removed and a CCA has been applied. Figure 6b indicates the

results of the network state after the GMR stage, where outlier edge connections have been identified and are represented in grey. A precision of 65% was achieved on identifying correct outlier connections with respect to MC truth. A fast convergence was achieved in extracting 6/7 candidates after the first stage and the remaining subgraphs are propagated to further stages.

Figure 5: Results of the GNN-based algorithm for track finding a) Simulated graph network where nodes $\sigma_e^2 > 0.8$ are removed and CCA is applied. Each colour represents a separate network. b) The extracted track candidates after GMR and Information Aggregation.

Figure 6: Results of the GNN-based algorithm described in Section 2 for track finding a) Simulated graph network where nodes with $\sigma_e^2 > 0.8$ are removed and CCA is applied. b) The resulting network state after Gaussian Mixture Reduction via clusterisation is applied. Outlier edge connections are masked and represented in grey. c) The extracted track candidates after stage 1.

3.2 Application for TrackML dataset

The TrackML dataset [2] consists of simulated measurements arranged using a model layout that is common to most Large Hadron Collider (LHC) experiments. The detectors span a cylindrical geometry where particle beams collide on the z axis around $z = 0$. This is the center of collision and also the center of the detector. The Pixel detector is closest to the beamline and is represented by volumes 7, 8 and 9 highlighted in blue, see Figure 7. For simplicity the model uses endcap volume 7 as the geometry consists of parallel silicon layers, hence the dataset used in this study is limited to volume 7. An example of an event viewed in endcap volume 7 can be seen in Figure 7b. Since the TrackML model can produce up to four hits per layer for any given track, clusters of hits are merged into nodes, ensuring exactly one node per layer [11].

Figure 7: TrackML detector layout and event simulation

Figure 8: Extracted track candidates and purity distributions for application of the GNN-based track finding on endcap volume 7 of the TrackML detector

The graph network is initialised with ~ 9000 nodes and $\sim 13,000$ edges, as well as with track state estimates using the same model as described in Section 3.1. However ongoing work is in development to use a more

precise approach using a parabolic model. A non-zero σ_{ou} parameter is used here to model the constant drift in ϕ due to the presence of the B-field, see Appendix A for process noise matrix Q . Edge connections are determined using a trained classifier and the predictions are converted into a look-up-table [11]. An initial CCA is applied to the graph network splitting the network into smaller subgraphs. After stage 1, the track splitting yielded 62% of track candidates successfully extracted uniformly at all ϕ , shown in Figure 8a.

The track reconstruction efficiency is the ratio of successfully reconstructed reference tracks to the total number of reference tracks in a given volume of interest. The efficiency obtained was 92% for fully contained tracks within endcap volume 7 with $p_T > 1\text{GeV}$. Particles with four or more hits contained within the endcap are considered and only proposed tracks with four or more hits are considered. Each track is matched with the ground truth majority particle sharing with it the greatest hit number. The ratio of this to the number of hits for the reconstructed track defines the track purity, whilst the ratio of this to the number of hits of the underlying particle defines the particle purity. Additionally, both the track purity and particle purity must be $> 50\%$. This criteria coincides with the definition of an accepted track candidate stated in the TrackML competition [2]. The resulting average track purity and particle purity for all extracted candidates is 99%. The purity distributions reflect that the application of the OU process works well for the given p_T range.

4 Conclusions

The approach developed here is a unique method using a GNN-based framework for track finding, unlike the traditional approach whereby Multi-Layered Perceptrons are trained to directly classify nodes and edges. By utilising various machine learning techniques, the graph network is allowed to learn local track parameters on its own by iteratively resolving ambiguities and discover track candidates. The main stages of the algorithm comprise of a Gaussian Mixture Reduction stage and neighbourhood information aggregation stage. The use of Kalman filters for both information aggregation and track extraction embedded into the network is a novel approach and has shown to successfully extract track candidates compatible with the particle motion model. The algorithm yields promising results on both a simple MC toy model and TrackML model for the endcap region. A preliminary result of $> 90\%$ track reconstruction efficiency is achieved for fully contained tracks within the endcap volume and with $p_T > 1\text{GeV}$. It is promising to see that this methodology provides a high performance on a small dataset, however the algorithm is still within the early stages of its development. An evaluation on the pixel barrel of the TrackML dataset is a work in progress, as well as within denser hit environments in order to sufficiently assess the quality of the algorithm.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The development of this project could not have been accomplished without the support and encouragement of my supervisors; Prof. Nikos Konstantinidis (UCL) and Dr. Dmitry Emelianov (RAL STFC).

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Appendix A Jacobian and Process Noise for track extraction KF

The three-dimensional KF implementation for track extraction. The state transition Jacobian F is derived using the OU model [7] and is given by the equations below, where $dx = x_i - x_j$. The parameter α of the OU model determines the stability of the rate of change of the track azimuthal angle and is initialised to 0.1. If $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$ the track model essentially becomes a straight line, however if $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, the model becomes a parabola. The state transition F is given by Eqn. 6,

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & dx & g_1 \\ 0 & 1 & f_1 \\ 0 & 0 & e_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where e_1 , f_1 and g_1 are given by the following equations.

$$e_1 = e^{-\alpha|dx|} \quad (7)$$

$$f_1 = \frac{1 - e_1}{\alpha} \quad (8)$$

$$g_1 = \frac{|dx| - f_1}{\alpha} \quad (9)$$

The process noise matrix Q is derived using the OU process [7] and is given by Eqn. 10, where σ_{ou} is initialised to 10^{-5} and σ_0 to 0.1,

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} (dx)^2(\sigma_{ms}^2 + \frac{(dx)^2\sigma_{ou}^2}{4}) & Q_{01} & Q_{02} \\ Q_{01} & \sigma_{ms}^2 + (dx)^2\sigma_{ou}^2 & Q_{12} \\ Q_{02} & Q_{12} & \sigma_{ou}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where Q_{01} , Q_{02} and Q_{12} are given by the following equations.

$$Q_{01} = dx(\sigma_{ms}^2 + Q_{02}) \quad (11)$$

$$Q_{02} = \frac{1}{2}(dx)^2\sigma_{ou}^2 \quad (12)$$

$$Q_{12} = dx\sigma_{ou}^2 \quad (13)$$